

D5.12 (Part 1, 2)

Chromosome number and karyotype of soil seed bank species report

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Deliverable 5.12 (Part 1, 2) Chromosome number and karyotype of soil seed bank species report

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Executive Summary

D5.12 Part 1 is a deliverable for Task T5.8, Land Management and Pollution: Impact on Plant Ploidy, within WP5, Soil Biodiversity. It outlines the background, objectives, initial results, and preliminary conclusions of Deliverable D5.12 Part 1, Chromosome Number and Karyotype Analysis of Soil Seed Bank Species, based on analyses conducted from the project's start (01.01.2023) until 31.12.2024.

1. Background and Aims

UoS led Task 5.8, “Land Management and Pollution: Impact on Plant Ploidy”, in collaboration with Spanish (UJA) and Greek (HMU, ELGO-D) partners to investigate the potential impact of pesticides on whole-genome duplication events in plants growing in the undergrowth of olive orchards under different cultivation systems (organic, traditional, and high-density intensive). This objective was pursued through cytogenetic analysis, including chromosome number determination and basic karyotype characterisation of plants obtained from seeds collected in olive groves. The results can be compared with reference values from the literature and relevant databases, allowing for the determination of the ploidy status of the investigated plant materials.

2. Initial Results

During the reporting period, UoS established or optimised detailed protocols to facilitate the analysis of chromosome numbers and basic morphometric karyotype characteristics across a spectrum of species. The collaborative partners were responsible for seed collection and provided six seed deliveries, comprising 232 seed entries from eight organic, ten traditional, and eight high-density intensive olive orchards in Spain, Greece, and Portugal. Drought occurring in numerous orchard locations during the 2023 and 2024 growing seasons hindered effective seed collection, causing delays in the analyses.

The taxonomic identity of the collected germplasm was determined at least to the genus level and, in many cases, to the species level, allowing for the identification of the most common taxa. Chromosome numbers were determined for 125 seed entries, representing 66 species and 39 genera. Additionally, basic karyotype characteristics, including the assessment of chromosome morphometric features, were analysed for 55 entries.

3. Preliminary conclusions

Due to limited orchard coverage, the current dataset is too incomplete to draw broad conclusions. However, once germplasm from all 53 locations, representing different cultivation types and all participating countries, becomes available, it should be feasible to gain a comprehensive understanding of the impact of pesticide use and cultivation type on whole-genome duplication events in plants growing in the undergrowth of olive orchards.